

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH ON THE ROLE OF PHARMACISTS IN OVERCOMING THE PROBLEM OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE

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Abstract

One of the most serious global threats to health and security is the spread of infectious diseases. In developing countries, infectious diseases are the leading cause of animal disease and account for more than 60% of the total human disease burden, posing a significant health risk to both humans and animals [1].

The article substantiates the expediency of improving consumer information counselling during the dispensing of antibiotics and defines the role of pharmacists in an interdisciplinary team working to overcome the problem of antibiotic resistance. Based on the data obtained, recommendations have been developed for pharmacists to optimise the practical aspects of dispensing antibacterial drugs, improve communication with patients and increase their adherence to the rational use of antibiotics.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Pharmaceutical care, Antibiotic stewardship, Pharmacist's role.

Aware of the serious consequences of the AMR problem, the WHO developed the Global Action Plan to tackle AMR (GAP-AMR) in 2015. This document was approved by governments around the world at the UN General Assembly in 2016. The goal of the GAP-AMR was to ensure the long-term continuity of successful treatment and prevention of infectious diseases through the use of effective and safe medicines that are of assured quality, responsibly used and accessible to all who need them [2].

On 22 October 2015, the WHO launched the Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS), which was the first international initiative to standardise antimicrobial resistance monitoring [3]. Since 2017, the WHO has been releasing annual GLASS reports describing the expansion and gradual strengthening of the newly created global system. At the end of 2021, 109 countries and two territories and regions were registered in the GLASS-AMR system.

The main goal of GLASS by 2030 is to ensure that all countries and territories participating in the system apply generally accepted standards for the collection and sharing of AMR information. This will contribute to a global surveillance system that informs the development of local, regional and global strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance.

From the outset, the GLASS-AMR programme focused on monitoring antimicrobial resistance in four

specific types of infections: bloodstream infections, gastrointestinal diseases, gonorrhoea and urinary tract infections. To this end, scientists identified eight types of bacteria that most commonly cause these infections and determined their sensitivity to 11 classes of antibacterial drugs, including 23 individual antibiotics. [3,4]

AMR is caused by a number of factors: human impact (excessive and incorrect use of antibiotics, weak infection control and insufficient information), animal husbandry practices (massive use of antibiotics in animal husbandry and aquaculture, transmission through food chains and direct contact), environmental influences (release of antibiotics and resistant bacteria into water, soil and waste), as well as factors related to wildlife (spread through contact with wild animals and destruction of their natural environment) [5].

Antimicrobial drugs are used in animal husbandry much more often than in human medicine, with their use exceeding the figures by 73–100%. This is due to the growing demand for animal protein from the middle class. A study of antimicrobial resistance found that the most life-threatening infections in 2019 were *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. According to

the report, these pathogens were responsible for approximately 929,000 deaths directly related to the development of antimicrobial resistance [6].

There are four main molecular mechanisms through which bacteria can express resistance to antimicrobial agents: modification of the target site, alteration or destruction of the drug, efflux of antimicrobial agents through efflux transporters, reduced penetration of antimicrobial agents through thickened membranes [7]. Bacteria that exhibit resistance to antibiotics may have gene(s) from internal, acquired, or adaptive sources.

In 2023, WHO developed Roadmap on antimicrobial resistance for the WHO European Region 2023–2030. The roadmap is organized around an AMR Compass that identifies five action areas and six enablers based on a combination of the best available evidence and expert opinion. For countries to adapt to their own national contexts. Each action area and enabler has a set of high-impact interventions and is intended as a practical and adaptable tool for countries to convene all relevant national AMR stakeholders, reach consensus on their priorities, set national targets and inform the investment cases for action on AMR [8].

The five areas of the Roadmap include the following directions: infection prevention and control and water, sanitation and hygiene; environmental and social determinants; stewardship; community awareness and enabling behaviours; access.

Strategy, the main recommendations for preventing the selection of antibiotic resistant strains are as follows:

- Control over the use of antibiotics in surgical hospitals.
- Epidemiological surveillance of postoperative infections and microbiological monitoring of antibiotic resistance in their causative agents.
- Prevention of nosocomial transmission of resistant strains of microorganisms in hospitals.
- Rational use of antibiotics in surgery involves:
- Elimination of the concept of "prophylactic treatment".
- Avoidance of treatment of previous colonization.
- Shortening the duration of antibiotic therapy courses.
- Intraoperative prophylaxis.

In 2017, the WHO Expert Committee on the Selection and Use of Essential Medicines developed the AWaRe (Access, Watch, Reserve) classification of antibiotics to support global efforts to manage their use at all levels of health care. The classification places antibiotics into three categories based on their use in treating common bacterial infections and their impact on antimicrobial resistance, emphasizing the need for appropriate use. In 2021, the AWaRe classification was updated to include 78 new antibiotics that had not previously been classified, bringing the total to 258 [9].

This classification is intended to be used as a tool for countries to better support antibiotic monitoring and stewardship activities. It is not intended as model for the inclusion of antibiotics on national essential medicine lists. Antibiotics classified under AWaRe and also

included on the WHO Model Lists of Essential Medicines are indicated in the worksheets. The "Access" group includes antibiotics that are effective against a wide range of commonly encountered susceptible pathogens, while also having a lower resistance potential compared to antibiotics in other groups. It comprises 86 antibiotics recommended for treating the 25 most common infections. These drugs should be universally available, of acceptable quality, and affordable. Selected antibiotics from the Access group are recommended as essential first- or second-choice empirical treatments for infectious syndromes, as reviewed by the Expert Committee on Essential Medicines, and are included as individual medicines on the Model Lists of Essential Medicines to improve access and promote appropriate use.

The "Watch" category includes most of the "highest-priority critically important antibiotics", which are recommended only for specific indications. The "Watch" category includes most of the "highest-priority critically important antibiotics," which are recommended only for specific indications. Includes 141 antibiotics. This group consists of antibiotic classes with a higher potential for resistance and includes many of the top-priority agents among Critically Important Antimicrobials for Human Medicine, as well as antibiotics at a relatively high risk of promoting bacterial resistance. These medicines should be key targets for stewardship programs and monitoring. Selected antibiotics from the Watch group are recommended as essential first- or second-choice empirical treatments for a limited number of specific infectious syndromes and are listed individually on the WHO Model Lists of Essential Medicines.

The "Reserve" category consists of antibiotics that should be used only as a last resort, such as for treating multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria, and only when all other antibiotics have failed. This group includes antibiotics and classes of antibiotics that should be reserved for the treatment of confirmed or suspected infections caused by organisms with multidrug resistance. Antibiotics from the Reserve group should be considered as "last resort" options. The Reserve group includes 28 antibiotics. Selected antibiotics from this group are listed as individual medicines in the WHO Model Lists of Essential Medicines if they have a favorable risk-benefit profile and proven activity against "critical priority" or "high priority" pathogens, as identified in the WHO Priority Pathogens List, particularly carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae. These antibiotics should be available but their use should be restricted to very specific patients and situations when all other alternatives have failed or are unsuitable.

These medicines should be protected and prioritized as key targets of national and international stewardship programs, which include monitoring and reporting on their use to preserve their effectiveness. WHO advises reducing the use of antibiotics from the "Watch" and "Reserve" groups while increasing access to and use of those in the "Access" group, with the goal that 60% of all antibiotic use in hospitals should come from the "Access" group.

Pharmacists play an important role in the fight against antimicrobial resistance. Their knowledge and

expertise can optimise the use of antimicrobials, reduce the risk of resistance and improve treatment efficacy. Pharmacists are often the first point of contact for patients and can have a real impact on antibiotic use.

Pharmacists are often the first point of contact for patients and can have a real influence on antibiotic use. Assessing the role of pharmacists as key intermediaries between the health care system and the patient, WHO published a report in 2014 summarising the experience of implementing antibiotic stewardship practices in 44 WHO European Member States. This document emphasises that pharmacists, along with regulators and physicians, play a key role in ensuring the correct use of antibiotics [10].

The main ways in which pharmacists contribute to this problem are:

- Counseling of healthcare professionals: Pharmacists provide information on the rational use of antibiotics, including drug selection, dosing, duration of treatment and monitoring of the efficacy and safety of therapy.

- Pharmacoepidemiological analysis: Analysis of antibiotic consumption data in a healthcare facility helps identify problem areas and propose measures to optimize antibiotic therapy.

- Development of protocols and algorithms: Pharmacists participate in the development of clinical protocols and algorithms for the management of patients with infectious diseases aimed at the rational use of antibiotics.

- Education: Conducting training for healthcare professionals and patients on the rational use of antibiotics increases awareness of the problem of antibiotic resistance and promotes behavior change.

- Monitoring side effects: Monitoring side effects of antibiotic therapy and participating in pharmacovigilance allow timely identification of problems associated with the use of antibiotics.

- Participation in programs to optimize the use of antibiotics: Active participation in the implementation of programs for the rational use of antibiotics at the level of a medical institution and region allows achieving more significant results.

Summarizing our research, we have identified key aspects of the role of a pharmacist in an interdisciplinary team to overcome antibiotic resistance. Pharmacists are an integral part of the interdisciplinary team aimed at combating antibiotic resistance. Their contribution to the optimization of antibiotic therapy, raising

awareness of the problem and the development of programs for the rational use of antibiotics helps slow the development of resistance and preserve the effectiveness of these vital drugs for future generations.

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